

COLREGs-compliant Planning Architecture For Autonomous Surface Vehicles

1st Samuele Depalo

*DIBRIS**

University of Genoa

Genoa, Italy

samuele.depalo@edu.unige.it

2nd Francesco Wanderlingh

DIBRIS and ISME†*

University of Genoa

Genoa, Italy

francesco.wanderlingh@unige.it

3rd Giovanni Indiveri

DIBRIS and ISME†*

University of Genoa

Genoa, Italy

giovanni.indiveri@unige.it

4th Enrico Simetti

DIBRIS and ISME†*

University of Genoa

Genoa, Italy

enrico.simetti@unige.it

Abstract—This paper presents a three-level planning architecture designed to enforce different international maritime rules (COLREGs), enhancing navigation safety and autonomy. The architecture consists of a global path planning layer for static obstacle avoidance, a local path planning layer incorporating dynamic obstacle data and COLREGs rules, and a reactive obstacle avoidance layer that addresses unexpected encounters in real-time. Preliminary tests at sea were conducted on the proposed approach, demonstrating its ability to achieve rules-compliant behaviour.

Index Terms—autonomous surface vehicles, path planning, colregs

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs) are increasingly employed in marine applications such as oceanographic analysis [1], bathymetric surveys [2], and surveillance [3]. To operate safely in these environments, ASVs must adhere to the “Convention on the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea” (COLREGs) [4], a set of navigation rules designed to prevent maritime accidents. Integrating COLREGs into ASV path planning and motion control systems poses a significant challenge, particularly in dynamic scenarios involving multiple moving obstacles.

Existing solutions have often approached COLREGs integration through reactive strategies (as in [5] [6]), leading to suboptimal paths and inefficient course corrections, or by focusing on only a subset of the rules. This paper proposes a novel planning architecture that addresses these issues by incorporating COLREGs rules into a three-level path planning structure [7]. Each level of this architecture is designed to apply different aspects of COLREGs, ranging from high-level global path planning to real-time local adjustments, thereby ensuring the ASV’s adherence to maritime navigation protocols.

II. PLANNING ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

The proposed architecture consists of three layers, as described below. For each layer, the specific COLREGs rules it enforces are identified, along with an explanation of how these rules are implemented.

* Dept. of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Systems Engineering (DIBRIS), University of Genoa, Via all’Opera Pia 13, 16145 Genova, Italy.

† Interuniversity Center of Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment (ISME), <https://isme.unige.it>.

A. Global Path Planning Layer

The global layer employs a visibility graph approach combined with Dijkstra’s algorithm to compute the optimal path from the ASV’s starting position to its target. This layer primarily considers static obstacles such as coastlines, buoys, and harbour structures. It preemptively enforces COLREGs applicable to these scenarios, including:

- Rule 9 (Narrow Channels): Ensures the ASV navigates along the starboard side of the channel.
- Rule 10 (Traffic Separation Schemes): Ensures compliance with established traffic lanes, facilitating smoother interaction with manned vessels.

The rules are enforced by an edge selection of the visibility graph that discards any connection whose relative motion is illegal, i.e., cutting the lanes, entering and exiting the lanes where it is not allowed, moving in the wrong side of the lane.

B. Local Path Planning Layer

This layer modifies the global path in response to dynamic obstacles (e.g., other vessels). It employs an A*-based algorithm that integrates kinematic data to account for the movement of nearby vessels, ensuring compliance with the following COLREGs rules:

- Rule 7 (Risk of Collision): Each obstacle is enclosed in a bounding box the ASV should not enter to avoid any risk of collision.
- Rule 8 (Actions to Avoid Collision): the ASV has to take appropriate actions to avoid collisions, this is enforced by following the rules hereafter.
- Rule 13 (Overtaking): The ASV must pass other vessels from a safe distance, altering its path to avoid conflicts.
- Rule 14 (Head-on Situation): When approaching another vessel head-on, the ASV alter its course to starboard.
- Rule 15 (Crossing Situation): The ASV gives way to vessels approaching from the starboard side, modifying its path accordingly.
- Rule 16 (Action by Give-way Vessel): The ASV, as the give-way vessel, takes early and substantial action to keep clear of the other vessel.
- Rule 18 (Responsibilities Between Vessels): The ASV respects the hierarchy of vessels (e.g., giving way to vessels restricted in their ability to maneuver, fishing vessels, or those not under command).

The planner generates waypoints for the ASV by identifying potential interception points with the vertices of obstacles' bounding boxes. Instead of conducting a grid-based search, the focus is on these specific points. The A* algorithm then evaluates possible maneuvers based on travel time and adherence to COLREGs. Maneuvers are inferred by the approaching angle of the ASV relative to the moving vessel, and their compliance is verified against a quantitative interpretation of the rules. Additionally, the planner retains a history of previously executed maneuvers to prevent consecutive prohibited actions, such as crossing a vessel's path after overtaking it.

C. Reactive Obstacle Avoidance Layer

The reactive layer is designed to handle unexpected encounters with obstacles that previous layers might not have detected. It operates in real-time, using sensor data to detect imminent collision risks and execute rapid maneuvers that conform to COLREGs rules, such as:

- Rule 17 (Action by Stand-on Vessel): If the give-way vessel fails to take avoidance countermeasures, the ASV must take evasive maneuvers to avoid a collision.
- Rule 19 (Conduct of Vessels in Restricted Visibility): the ASV should avoid sudden turns to port and generally alter course to starboard to maintain safety. It should also avoid altering course toward a vessel abeam or abaft.

Implementing Rule 19 poses significant challenges because, unlike human operators, ASVs rely solely on sensor data, complicating the translation of Rule 19's guidance into an algorithmic framework. This necessitates further research and development to achieve effective implementation.

III. PRELIMINARY TESTS

Preliminary tests targeting specific COLREGs rules were conducted on the second layer of the architecture. These tests initially took place in a simulated environment using the dynamic model of the ULISSE, an autonomous catamaran developed by ISME, in a software-in-the-loop fashion. Subsequently, the experiments were performed at sea with the actual robot and simulated obstacles. An example of these tests, featuring three moving vessels, where the ASV successfully avoid the obstacles, is illustrated and described in Fig. 1. Currently, the first and third layers remain under development and are scheduled for evaluation in future trials.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a COLREGs-compliant planning architecture for ASVs that effectively integrates navigation rules across three hierarchical levels. Through preliminary testing, the system demonstrated its ability to assess collision risks and execute appropriate maneuvers. The successful implementation of this system has significant implications for the future of autonomous maritime navigation, particularly in ensuring that ASVs can operate alongside manned vessels safely.

Future work will focus on extensive trials of the complete architecture in diverse maritime scenarios to evaluate its performance, robustness, and adherence to COLREGs. Additionally, engaging experienced seafarers is essential to validate the

Fig. 1. The catamaran moves to goal while avoiding the upcoming vessels. The blue and red lines are planned path, while the orange line is the actually traveled route. t_0 : the computed path to goal (blue line) aims at the opposite direction the catamaran has; t_1 : the planner realize there is a new optimal path (red line) due to the catamaran delay in following the previous path.

system's interpretation and application of COLREGs rules, ensuring that the quantitative approximation aligns with practical maritime standards. This includes addressing Rule 6, which mandates maintaining a safe speed and requires a context-awareness tool that needs to be fine-tuned by seafarers to allow the algorithm to suggest optimal speeds based on the number and size of nearby vessels.

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